

Women's Empowerment – Education as a Tool for Achieving Equality in Indian Society

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Abstract

The focus of the study is achieving women equality in Indian society through education. Education is a vital tool for women empowerment, prosperity, equality, progression and welfare. The inequality and vulnerability of women in all sectors and women oppressed in all spheres of life, they want to be empowered in all the corners of life. To fight against the socially constructed gender biases, women have to swim against the system that requires more power. Such power comes from the process of empowerment and it can be acquired by the way of education. The findings of the study is that educational qualification plays a significant role in women empowerment and it concludes that if women's empowerment is effected, it can be carried out only through the medium of education. Hence, it is foremost significant to raise the level of education amongst women in society.

Keywords: women's empowerment, equality, education, society.

Introduction

"Education creates people simple to lead, but hard to drive; easy to govern but not possible to enslave."

– William Blake

Education surrounds not only the teaching but also the learning of knowledge, right conduct and practical capability. Learning includes the moral values and improvement of character and methods to increase the strength of mind. Education forms character, strengthens mind, increases knowledge and makes us independent. Education dispels ignorance. Education is a reform for the human mind. Without education, the guidance of the human mind is deficient. The human mind was made to be skilled and lack of education, a person is imperfect. Literacy makes the women; think in the right way and capable to be a sound decision-maker. And this can only be attained by the education which appraises a woman with knowledge of the world around her and beyond teaches her to reason and acquaints her with history so that they can be a better judge of the present.

Without education, Woman is like one who is confined to a closed room with no place to exit or entry and completely shut from the outside world. But education lends woman into the open world. An uneducated woman cannot read and write, and hence, she is closed

to all the knowledge and wisdom that she can gain through books and other channels. Uneducated or less educated have less opportunity to live a life of their choice. A woman that gets an education will be more to the avenues for life of his choice. Educated women will be a better citizen and an intelligent decision-maker. This is the reason why people always prefer an educated or more educated person over an uneducated or the less-educated person for employment purposes even to do a job which does not require much of education, like an office attendant or domestic help.

Each individual has a special level of understanding and knowledge however education refines and enhances them. Thus, the importance of education can never be damaged. All over the country people agree that education is the key to a healthy mind and a successful life.

By empowering women, it will automatically strengthen the national economy. According to the Literacy Rate 2011 census, the female literacy level is 65.46%, whereas the male literacy rate is over 80%. Education measured as a landmark for women empowerment. Education is the only key to unlock the golden door of freedom for development. Education plays a core role in supporting women's right, dignity and security. The Government also has given more magnitude for education, so more priority was specified in the national policy. The focus of the Government is mainly targeting on illiteracy and endeavouring hard to eradicate illiteracy. Government is conducting various literacy programmes like adult literacy programme, continuing education programme, weekend and part-time study programme, mid-day meal programme, free-education programme, etc. to increase the percentage of literacy in the country. The success rates of these programmes are gradual. Education is one of the most critical areas of empowerment for women.

Education – “A boon to Women’s Empowerment”:

Knowledge is the power and every Indian woman has to acquire it through literacy. It outcomes with the experience that she gains from the environment and the supportive world around her, which allow her to live as experienced productive members of the society.

An educated woman makes the environment homely with her better decision- making power. Mother's love and affection are the primary sources of learning for the child to know extremely necessary things of the environment. Literacy is a boon to a woman to tackle the problems in the society with self-confidence, courage, strength and positive thoughts. It is also helpful for a woman to know their legal rights and fight for equality in the society. Educated women analyse the problems in correct way and take the proper solution to solve the problem. Analysis of problem and critical thinking shapes the women to be a better member and maintains an important position in society.

Women and girls practice numerous and intersecting inequalities. Some structural barriers in the social, political, economic and environmental spheres create and strengthen these inequalities. Hurdles to women's social, economic and political empowerment, and violence not in favor of women and girls, are barriers to sustainable growth and the attainment of human rights, gender equality, impartiality and harmony. Transversely man of the countries, either by law or custom, women are still denied the right to own land or inherit property, acquire access to credit, be present at school, get income and progress in their profession free from job bias. Women are significantly under-represented in decision-making at all levels. Although the economic advantages of educating girls are parallel to those of educating boys, recent findings suggest the social benefits are greater.

Source: Department of Education, Ministry of Human Resource & Development

The above diagram represents the comparative educational status of men and women in 2001 and 2011. The literacy rate of men and women are 76.26 and 53.67 in 2001 but there is a gradual growth in the year of 2011. The literacy rate of 2011 for men is 82.14 and women are 65.46. Hence the literacy rate was improved but not achieved a sufficient level of growth.

Women have the potential power to modify their individual monetary status and that of their communities and countries in which they live yet typically women’s economic contributions are unrecognized, their work underestimated and their assurance starved. Uneven opportunities between women and men hinder women’s ability to lift themselves from poverty and secure improved options to improve their lives. Literacy is the most leading instrument for changing women’s place in society. The only way of reducing poverty is involving the girl children in the field of education.

Higher education leads a woman to “Complete living” in society

Self-possession

Learning helps the women not only in obtaining knowledge but also enables her to produce a living with the potential willpower and self-confident in society.

Family welfare

The woman who has the knowledge of literacy leads and plays an important role in a family. They handle the finance and health care and other welfare of the family.

Participation in Social and political events

Higher education creates women to have a good accepting of social and political processes afar the home in far-reaching social structure and makes her a wise citizen with effective social and political actions.

Requirement of life

Money is a need in maintaining life and education helps in preserving life.

All these are not adequate for an entire living if a woman does not believe

- Moral Value
- Divine value
- Group Value
- Logical Value

Learning of education motivates the women to be mentally and psychologically stronger and to face challenges and defeat obstacles in life and to be an absolute woman. It molds the women stronger to tackle the problems in the family as well as society.

Responsibility of Indian Government in Promoting Gender Equity in Education

From the total population of India, women conquer nearly 48%. Equity in education particularly gender equity was one of the most significant issues in India and, there has been a remarkable growth in women joining for higher education while independence (increased to 42%), dropping the gender gap in higher education. Women enrolled 14.72% in professional courses and the highest percent of enrolment in Goa and the lowest percent of enrolment in Bihar.

After independence, several commissions and committees set up in India promoted its must for gender parity in all the stages of education. Kothari commission and the national policy on education and the programme of Action in 1992 put a massive stress on support of gender equity in education by sinking the gender gap in access, preservation and evolution from one stage to other. The national policy on education stressed that literacy will be used as a mediator of basic change in the status of women. In order to neutralized the accumulated disadvantages of the past. The national policy for empowerment of women has been a remarkable achievement for women. The year 2001 was notable as women's empowerment year, which accepted women India continues to give confidence higher education for women through some programmes like Indira Gandhi scholarship for single girl child scheme for pursuing higher and in order to support higher education through scholarships and by constructing women hostels and by capacity building for women managers in higher education.

The Following Approaches have been Prepared During the XI Plan,

- To arrange the training programmes, concentrated on rising sensitivity to gender issues in respect of women managers.
- To make ability of building a women's movement.
- To engage the Principals of the colleges or Vice-chancellors of the Universities in the improvement of the programme.

The Indian Government has established different schemes, cells and academies for the progression of women education in the society.

- Equal Opportunities Cells (EOC)
- PRAGATI - Scholarships for Girl Child for Technical education
- Residential Coaching Academy
- Post-Doctoral Fellowship
- UDAAN Program
- Swami Vivekananda Scholarship for Single Girl Child for research in Social Sciences

“Equal Opportunities Cells (EOC)” was setup by the Government of India particularly for ST/SC/OBC/Minorities. The focus of the cell is to develop Social Group Equity all over the country. The UGC has guided and assisted institutions to set up “Equal opportunity Cells” to administer the efficient implement and achievement of policies and programmes for disadvantaged groups and to offer assistance and counselling in social, cultural, academic, financial and other matters. The other concentration area of the cell is to sensitize University/ Colleges on troubles faced by Scheduled Caste (SC) and Scheduled Tribe (ST) categories in higher education.

The Government introduced the scheme to be exact “PRAGATI - Scholarships for Girl Child for Technical education”. The objective of the scheme is encouraging and supporting the girl child to obtain technical education. The scheme also providing the amount of scholarship Rs.30000 and tuition fees Rs.2000 for 10 months until the duration of the course. As per the statistical survey, with the constraint of only one girl per family with the income of the family less than 6 lakhs per annum, the number of girls benefited nearly 4000. The qualified candidates will be selected on the basis of merit through the qualifying examination and interview conducted by the concern state of the country.

“Residential Coaching Academy” was the academy setup by the Government of India. The academy is setup only for SC/ST/Minorities and women in Universities and Colleges. The objective of the scheme is to give proper coaching to the students for NET and All India & State Civil Services examinations and UG/ PG level examinations.

Another initiative scheme of the Indian Government is “Post-Doctoral Fellowship”. The main concentration of the scheme is SC/ST and Women & Post-Graduate Scholarships for SC/ST students and the students those who are studying Post Graduate in professional courses.

CBSE initiated the “UDAAN” program for the development of girl child education, so as to promote the admission of girl students. The motto the program is to address the teaching gap between school education and engineering entrance examinations. It seeks to boost the enrolment of girl students in prestigious technical education institutions through incentives & academic support. It offers free online supplementary lessons in the particular subjects’ math, physics and chemistry, specially prepared in the form of videos, text and practice tests on a tablet.

Comparing to the boys, the withdraw ratio at various levels of education for girls is much higher. Observing the thoughts of Swami Vivekananda, freedom for women and equality of women in the society as well as the nation can be possible with the help of education. UGC has announced the “Swami Vivekananda Scholarship for Single Girl Child for research in Social Sciences”. The motto of this scheme is to compensate direct costs of higher education particularly for such girls who are the only girl child in their family.

The given below are some of the causes for Indian women grading for Higher Education:

- Support by the Indian Government and Society
- Capability to merge studies and work with family life
- Decreasing discrimination against girls in families
- Maximum groundwork for higher education.

Source: Ministry of Human Resource Development

Where as the gross enrolment ratio for young men was 24.5, for young women, it was 22.7 in 2014-15, an improvement from 17.9 in 2012-13. The figure of young men enrolled in higher education improved 13% to 17.9 million in 2014-15, from 15.8 million in 2012-13, and the number of young women enrolled increased 21% to 15.3 million from 12.6 million.

Conclusion

“Education is the success key for Women Empowerment”

The Government of India places education at the core of women’s ability to give to all activities, working to improve knowledge, competency and skills, including in the development process and in their contributions to civil society. Education is a beautiful ornament for women to wear.

Education enriches not only the knowledge but also the empowerment. It is also necessary for reducing poverty and reaching sustainable development. In all the schemes, the Government of India shows its unique concentration to develop the women education. In recent years, women in modern society are so smart and independent that she can be simply called a superwoman. Women in India are approaching up in all spheres of life. Maximum number of women is joining in the universities and colleges to improve their position in society. They are getting into all kinds of professions like engineering, medicine, politics, teaching, etc. A nation’s improvement and success can be estimated by the way how it treats its women folk.

The study finally concluded that through the schemes, programmes, projects and some major steps taken by the Government in the field of education, particularly for women help to attain equality in the society. At the same moment, the progression of women empowerment realizes the goal in society through education.

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